

Impact of diabetes mellitus on quality of life in patients with or without islet autotransplantation after total pancreatectomy

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Introduction

Islet autotransplantation (IATx) is an optional treatment for patients undergoing total pancreatectomy (TP) for non-malignant reasons. According to reported data, the general quality of life significantly improves (based mainly on pain relief). In 30% of cases, the IATx prevents diabetes development. The rest of the patients remain on less or more intensive insulin therapy. Therefore, the presented study aimed to determine the impact of diabetes on the patient quality of life.

Methods

Patients were divided into two groups and monitored at least for three months. The first one included patients after TP treated with IATx (n=9). The second group comprised patients after TP without subsequent IATx (n=9). All of them filled out the ADQOOL questionnaire validated for quality of life in patients with diabetes. Six parameters evaluated diabetes compensation: (The mean HbA1c, The mean time in range (TIR), The mean glycemia, Variation coefficient, Time in hypoglycemia and hyperglycemia).

Results

IATx improved significantly the diabetes compensation in comparison to the control group (the mean HbA1c was 50.4 ± 8 vs. 66.2 ± 13 mmol/mol, $p=0,036$; Time in range 84 ± 15 % vs. 51.4 ± 19 % $p=0.0017$). Their mean glycemia was lower (7.4 ± 1.4 mmol/l vs. 10.2 ± 2.1 mmol/l, $p=0.004$), and the variation coefficient was better (25 ± 5 % vs. 37 ± 5 %). Time in hypoglycemia did not differ between groups (2.4 ± 2.1 % vs. 4.6 ± 3.5 % $p=0.15$).

In general, patients after IATx felt their quality of life was “very good” in comparison to people after TP who consider their lives as “not good, not bad” (average weighted impact score AWI 2 ± 0.6 vs. 0.6 ± 1.0). If they did not have diabetes, they would feel their lives were the same (AWI score -0.6 ± 0.48 for the AITX group vs. -2 ± 0.63 for the TP only group).

Conclusion

IATx resulted in significantly better diabetes compensation and significantly reduced perception of diabetes negative impact on their life well-being.

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